

Thermal Decomposition and Dielectric Relaxation Studies of Zinc(II) Stearate

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Manuscript received 11 November 1975 ; revised 29 January 1976 ; accepted 11 March 1976

Conventional methods require time variation and temperature variation as two distinct stages in the evaluation of the kinetics of a reaction and its energy of activation. The method used by Freeman and Carroll can determine both the order and the energy of activation in one stage experiment by keeping the change in temperature with time uniform. The present authors have carried out the thermal decomposition studies of Zn(II) stearate by this method and have found the order of the reaction as nearly zero and the energy of activation as 9.83 Kcals/mole.

Dielectric relaxation times τ were determined at 0.26MHz frequency on dilute solutions of Zn(II) stearate at temperatures 30°, 60° and 70° and temperature/concentration dependence of τ has been discussed.

IN recent years, there has been renaissance of interest in thermal dissociation studies of inorganic compounds. However, it is found that it is difficult to correlate thermal stability with all the properties of the compound. One property, nevertheless, namely the order and the energy of activation of the decomposition reaction of a compound, can definitely be correlated with its thermal decomposition.

In the present paper, thermal decomposition of Zn(II) stearate has been investigated by the method given by Freeman and Carroll¹. The most important condition in the conduct of experiment is that dT/dt is absolutely constant. This condition was adhered to in the present investigation keeping the rate change 0.509° per minute.

Freeman and Carroll method : In a reaction of the type studied in this investigation, where the reactant disappears continuously with time and temperature and one product is gaseous, the rate expression for the decomposition of A can be written in the form :

$$-dc/dt = K C^n \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where the symbols have their usual meaning.

Starting with this elementary expression, Freeman and Carroll¹ have derived a relation :

$$\frac{-E}{2.3R} \Delta \left(\frac{1}{T} \right) = -n + \frac{\Delta \log dw/dt}{\Delta \log W_r} \quad (2)$$

where E = energy of activation,
n = order of reaction,

dw/dt = values obtained from the loss-time curve.

$W_r = W_c - W$ (W_c being total loss and W the loss at time t)

Since this relation can be cast in the form of $y = mx + c$, it is evident that the slope $m = -E/2.3R$ and the intercept $n =$ the order of reaction.

The procedure for obtaining the rate constant and the energy of activation of decomposition, in one single operation, is divided into two stages : (i) Plot loss in the sample vs time and from the graph, by drawing tangents or otherwise, determine dw/dt and, (ii) estimate W_r from the total loss at infinite time t and loss at any predetermined time t i. e. $W_r = W_c - W$ and then plot $(\Delta \log (dw/dt) / \Delta \log W_r)$ vs $(1/\Delta T \Delta \log W_r)$. From the plots the order of the reaction and the energy of activation is obtained.

Experimental

Preparation of Zn(II) stearate : Zinc stearate was prepared by double decomposition of zinc chloride and sodium stearate in benzene solution. Excess of sodium stearate was added to prevent possible hydrolysis. The precipitate was washed several times with hot water till it was free from chloride ions and then with cold benzene. The salt was recrystallised from hot benzene and dried in partial vacuum at 60°. All the chemicals were extremely pure.

Analysis :

	C	H	Zn
Found	68.14	10.96	10.31
Calcd. for Zn C ₃₆ H ₇₀ O ₄	68.42	11.08	10.35

The set up for thermal decomposition studies was assembled in the laboratory. A right-angled bent tube was attached to the pan of Metler Semi-micro balance reading accurately upto the fifth place of decimal. The sample was heated in a stainless steel cup attached to the right angled bent tube in an electric furnace assembled at BARC, Bombay and the temperature was

controlled by a variac and sunvic automatic switch. The temperature was read by an alumel-chromel thermocouple in conjunction with a precision Cambridge-Pyepotentiometer (No. 7558) which registered voltage upto a milli-volt accurately. The results were obtained in duplicate, and found to be consistent.

The dielectric constants (ϵ') and dielectric losses (ϵ'') of Zinc(II) stearate were recorded on a DK-06 multi-decameter (made in Germany (WTB)). The decameter was tested by determining the dipole moments of nitrobenzene by the method prescribed by Gopalkrishna³.

Results and Discussion

Results of the decomposition are given in Table 1, while Table 2 gives the treatment of data according to Freeman and Carroll. Rate of reaction in a heterogeneous medium like the present one is given by

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = r_e \times \theta^m \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

where r_e is the rate of evaporation of the product and θ is a measure of the surface concentration of the reacting molecules.

This can be shown to be equal to

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{K_1 p}{K_2 p + 1} \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

where K_1, K_2 are constants and p is the pressure of gaseous product. When the surface is completely covered by the product, $\frac{dx}{dt}$ becomes constant or in other words the process is kinetically of zero order. There is every possibility that when the decomposition is fast, the molecules under investigation remain covered completely all the time and the rate of decomposition is independent of concentration. From the results given in Table 1 and 2 and graphically represented in Fig. 1 and 2, it is seen that such is the state in the present investigation. A similar investigation by Murgulescue and Segal⁵ on nickel ammonia complex showed that the thermal decomposition of the salt took place in one

TABLE 2—FREEMAN-CARROLL TYPE OF PLOTS.

$\frac{\Delta \log(dw/dt)}{\Delta \log W_r}$	$\frac{\Delta(1/T)}{\Delta \log W_r} \times 10^3, \text{ } ^\circ\text{K}^{-1}$
6.19360	2.871
5.67797	2.599
5.49441	2.428
4.50164	2.099
4.11798	1.881
3.74564	1.678
2.04552	0.991
1.58500	0.664

The plots of W vs t (in min) and $\Delta \log(dw/dt)/\Delta \log W_r$ vs $\Delta(1/T)/\Delta \log W_r$ are shown in Fig. 1 and 2. dw/dt was obtained from the curve in Fig. 1 by drawing tangents at the appropriate temperatures. It is seen (Fig. 2) that n , the order of reaction comes out to be nearly zero and the energy of activation 9.83 Kcals/mole.

single step thus resulting in zero order. The same authors have reported the decomposition of $\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4 \cdot \text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ in two steps, each step corresponding to zero order, activation energies being in the range of 15 Kcals/mole for each step.

Fig. 1.

TABLE 1—(dT/dT=0.509°/MIN ; STARTING TEMP. 77° WHEN THE DECOMPOSITION STARTS. TOTAL LOSS 350 MINUTES AFTER, 0.10390g.)

Minutes (from the start)	Temp. °K	W(g)	W _r (g)
50	350.00	.00125	.10175
100	375.55	.00964	.09425
150	400.90	.01050	.09340
175	413.60	.0334	.07050
200	426.30	.0457	.05820
250	451.80	.0559	.04800
260	456.89	.0977	.00620
300	477.25	.1032	.00070
320	487.46	.1039	—
350	502.76	.1030	—

Fig. 2.

The conclusion that can be drawn from the thermal decomposition results of Zn(II) stearate is that the reaction takes place in a single step and is of zero order, the activation energy being in the range of ~ 10 Kcal/mole.

Relaxation time τ : The relaxation times (τ) of the zinc(II) stearate in benzene solution was determined at frequencies ranging from KH_z to MH_z (1.26×10^6 to 1.5×10^8). Table 3 sets out the ϵ' and ϵ'' values measured. From Cole-Cole plots, α parameters were obtained and from these and the values of v/u (method given by Smyth and Hennelly and Heston⁶) τ values were determined. These τ values are set out in Table 4.

concentration changes roughly four fold, the τ values increase approximately to the same extent, the trend seen in the concentration— τ relation being not observed in temperature — τ relation.

In the micelle, the molecules are held together by the strong attractive forces around their polar end groups. The existence of these forces is demonstrated by the tenacity with which the metal soaps hold on the water and their presence explains the paradox of their simultaneous insolubility in water and the ease of taking water of hydration⁷. If the picture presented by rubber molecules which has strong chemical bonds along the parallel chains of isoprene units and weak van der

TABLE 3—DIELECTRIC CONSTANTS (ϵ') AND LOSSES (ϵ'') AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF ZINC(II) STEARATE AND AT VARYING FREQUENCIES (TEMPS. 30°, 60° AND 70°).

Temp. 32°		(Concentration in weight fractions)		Temp. 70°	
		Temp. 60°			
Conc. 2.11×10^{-4}					
ϵ'	ϵ''	ϵ'	ϵ''	ϵ'	ϵ''
2.27750	0.27684	2.22962	0.27681	2.21870	0.26637
2.27680	0.21390	2.22936	0.20866	2.21730	0.25889
2.27470	0.19690	2.22870	0.15050	2.21450	0.21139
2.27442	0.14574	2.22856	0.14746	2.21422	0.18532
2.27330	0.14436	2.22730	0.08233	2.21296	0.12938
2.27148	0.07762	2.22248	0.07916	2.21254	0.12577
2.27120	0.06411	2.22126	0.07407	2.21030	0.06504
2.27085	0.03781				
2.27075	0.02752				
Conc. 0.84×10^{-4}					
ϵ'	ϵ''	ϵ'	ϵ''	ϵ'	ϵ''
2.27592	0.28800	2.22990	0.27146	2.21398	0.25668
2.27495	0.26900	2.22808	0.20665	2.20890	0.24965
2.27390	0.20025	2.22710	0.20168	2.20580	0.17751
2.27293	0.19417	2.22430	0.13722	2.20150	0.10449
2.27185	0.13442	2.22290	0.13324	2.20040	0.10043
2.27176	0.13061	2.22108	0.10752	2.19900	0.07619
2.27162	0.06469	2.22094	0.05284	2.19340	0.03476
Conc. 0.6×10^{-4}					
ϵ'	ϵ''	ϵ'	ϵ''	ϵ'	ϵ''
2.27582	0.27684	2.23130	0.27418	2.21360	0.22058
2.27470	0.20761	2.22570	0.26122	2.21250	0.20558
2.27388	0.20261	2.22290	0.19688	2.20890	0.14574
2.27290	0.14574	2.22164	0.14870	2.20750	0.14436
2.27190	0.14436	2.21968	0.13194	2.20680	0.07547
2.27134	0.07343	2.21856	0.07407	2.20530	0.06695
2.27105	0.06901	2.21694	0.06005		
2.27008	0.03174				

It is seen from the data (Table 4) that generally the order of the relaxation times of Zn(II) stearate at 0.26 MH_z is 10^{-7} sec. Zinc stearate is a micelle having colloidal properties. This is borne out by the observation that the relaxation time increases from 3×10^{-7} to about 11×10^{-7} secs as the concentration of Zn(II) stearate rises from $0.63 \times 10^{-4} M$ to $2.11 \times 10^{-4} M$. With the rise of temperature from 30° to 70° τ values generally increase e. g. at $0.68 \times 10^{-4} M$ concentration $\tau_{32^\circ} = 0.97 \times 10^{-7}$ sec, and $\tau_{60^\circ} = 1.82 \times 10^{-7}$ sec and $\tau_{70^\circ} = 3.43 \times 10^{-7}$ sec. However, the results indicate that τ values are rather concentration dependent than temperature dependent. Since it is observed that when

TABLE 4—RELAXATION TIMES (τ VALUES) OF ZINC(II) STEARATE AS A FUNCTION OF TEMPERATURE AND CONCENTRATION (IN WEIGHT FRACTION)

Conc. $\times 10^{-4}$ (wt. fractions)	τ values $\times 10^7$ sec.		
	32°	60°	70°
0.63	0.979	1.817	3.425
0.84	1.822	2.937	5.988
2.11	3.978	4.570	11.140

Waals forces perpendicular to the chains is mirrored for Zn(II) stearate molecules, then it can be argued that with the rise of concentration the strong chemical linkage along the chains namely, metal-carboxylic links, get augmented with the increase of number of molecules and so also the intermolecular bonds and hence the relaxation time increases in the same order as the concentration. With the rise of temperature, however, it seems the weak intermolecular bonds are severed, though the chemical linkages along the chain appear to remain almost unaffected. The rise in relaxation times, therefore, are only three fold with temperature rise as against four fold with the concentration rise as can be seen from the results set out in Table 4, the results at 30° being taken as those at almost room temperature.

Acknowledgement

The authors gratefully thank Dr. D. D. Khanolkar, Professor and Head, Department of Chemistry, Marathwada University, for taking keen interest throughout the conduct of this work.

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